

METHODS OF TEACHING HISTORY IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION.

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Abstract: A student with special educational needs in the Republic of Uzbekistan involving children in inclusive education. Types of disabilities in inclusive education to study the proportionality of the reforms that should be made in this regard increase efficiency. Methods of teaching history.

Key words: Education, children, disability, inclusive education, social adaptation, principle of comprehensive approach.

"Inclusive education" does not include this definition. It only mentions that "inclusive education is equal treatment of all children, including children with physical or mental disabilities, excluding any form of discrimination during education." Galina Nam, a researcher of inclusive education in Uzbekistan and a doctoral student at the University of Waikato in New Zealand, said that it should be a priority for children with disabilities to be educated in general educational institutions, not in special boarding schools or at home. It is necessary to give consent to studying in places and at home only in special cases. The right to choose an educational institution should remain with the children themselves and their parents and their legal representatives," says Galina Nam. Inclusive education creates equal opportunities for children with special needs and healthy children. UNICEF deals with the issues of inclusion of inclusive education in the education system of Uzbekistan. The mission of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and circumstances. At the same time, the principle of inclusion implies that children with limited opportunities should live in a family and study together with their peers in a regular school in order to have a positive mental and social development. An inclusive education system ensures that a child in a wheelchair attends a nearby school, receives special support for learning to read and write if he/she is struggling, and provides appropriate support for returning to school for a child who does not attend classes.

The essence of this principle is that since 1990, several declarations and decisions have been made on the world level regarding the education of children with special needs in the system of general education institutions. Many countries of the world recognized them. But to date there are many problems in their implementation. In some countries, when laws or decisions on general education are adopted, the issue of education of disabled children is not included in it. But the recognition of inclusive education will not depend only on passing laws. Fighting discrimination and social prejudice is the most important thing. In other words, the first thing to do is to carry out propaganda among the population, recognizing inclusive education.

From this it can be understood that inclusive education includes children with disabilities not only in special schools, but general education where healthy children are studying it is determined that it is appropriate for them to study in their schools. And for that pedagogic staff, educators, parents and children are included in the inclusive education system readiness, school level, physical conditions and the factors that make it possible to study this education must fully meet the requirements. Children with special needs are also healthy peers to work at the level of one's own ability, get education, profession able to learn and develop. 1990 A very important conference in Thailand was conducted. This conference aims to formulate the goal of

"Education for All".155 countries and more than 150 non-governmental organizations added ones. The held conference showed that; about 10-15 percent are children identified as needing special education. Currently, 250,000 ha in Uzbekistan Children with disabilities (under 16 years of age) of various forms have a need for education. The number of special educational institutions is 86 and covers the following areas.

As for the subject of history, it deals with the events that happened before. History. The topics in the program are usually far from the everyday life and experiences of the students. Many historical relics and materials from the past to the present are around us Although it exists, history is found as an abstract subject in its content possible Due to this feature of the history lesson, especially young students have trouble understanding events that happened long before their time will come. In other words, without connecting history with today because of the effort to teach, some students find history class boring, An incomprehensible series consists of numbers, figures and objects. History and historical processes, political-historical situation are the main factors in their occurrence comprehensive analysis in scientific research of causes and features is considered a major factor in the emergence of historical truth. Especially in different eras in the created historical scientific works, the research questions of the authors are different approaches and opinions, differences of conclusions, their scientific in-depth analysis making and the most correct conclusions based on historical, scientific and objectivity It is one of the important tasks facing today's historians is counted. Today, students who study in the field of history are about history methods of mastering such as using works, analyzing them, from them Historical research methods and scientific-historical knowledge of the effectiveness of use he should understand the ways to reach the truth.

Conclusion: Up to now, in the schools of the regions of our republic organized inclusive classes take their work activities as an experiment, a test are going In order to introduce the idea of inclusive education in Uzbekistan and to solve its problems, organizing various measures, promotion and campaigning through the media became somewhat more active.

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